

ViVIM, Visió per computador per Vídeo Immersiu Multi-plataforma

LL3.3.1: Programari de transmissió i recepció multi-plataforma

This deliverable reports on the first functional version for each of the listed tools / components. Future versions of this deliverable will provide a comprehensive review of the evolution of such tools, along with the different released versions for each of them.

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable reports on a set of software components and tools developed to enable the multi-platform delivery (i.e. processing, transmission and reception) of different content modalities in diverse use cases considered in the ViViM project. In particular, the deliverable reports on the next five software components: (i) editing and storytelling tool (Adobe Premier Pro plugin) for multi-format and multi-screen experiences; (10) cloud-based Orchestrator; (10i) in-sync multi-stream and low latency Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) delivery pipeline; (iv) RGB-D transmission pipeline for holo-portation, and (v) remote rendering plugin, from 3D Virtual Reality (VR) scenarios to 2D web-based players using Web Real-Time Communication (WebRTC) technology. For each tool, the following documentation is added: (i) its relationship with state-of-the-art contributions; (10) its components and modules, together with architectural aspects; (10i) linked requirements that the tool accomplishes / provides; (iv) system requirements and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); (v) information and guides on how to install, run and access the code; and (vi) its roadmap within the project's lifetime. All these contributions are provided within the scope of Task 3.3 "Software tools for multi-platform delivery and reception", addressed within Activity 3 "Tools for Immersive Media Production" of the ViViM project. This is the first version of LL3.3 to be updated and extended in upcoming iterations, with new tools, new features and optimized implementations.</p>
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Table of Acronyms:

AMI	Amazon Machine Image
ASF	Apache Software Foundation
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CMAF	Common Media Application Format
CMP	Cubemap Projection
CoD	Content-on-Demand
DASH	Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP
ERP	Equirectangular Projection
FoV	Field of View
HAS	HTTP Adaptive Streaming
HDMI	High Definition Multimedia Interface
HLS	HTTP Live Streaming
HMD	Head Mounted Display
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LGPL	Lesser General Public License
MCU	Multipoint Control Unit
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RTMP	Real Time Messaging Protocol
RTSP	Real Time Streaming Protocol
SFU	Selective Forwarding Unit
TURN	Traversal Using Relays around NAT
VR	Virtual Reality

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives of this deliverable

This deliverable reports on the software tools developed within the scope of Task 3.3 “*Software tools for multi-platform delivery and reception*”, addressed within Activity 3 “*Tools for Immersive Media Production*” of the ViVIM project. In particular, the deliverable reports on five different software tools in this version of the deliverable, namely: (i) editing and storytelling tool (Adobe Premier Pro plugin) for multi-format and multi-screen experiences; (10) cloud-based Orchestrator; (10i) in-sync multi-stream and low latency delivery pipeline; (iv) RGB-D transmission pipeline for holo-portation, and (v) remote rendering plugin, from 3D scenarios to 2D web-based players. For each tool, the deliverable reports on: (i) its relationship with state-of-the-art contributions; (10) its components and modules, together with architectural aspects; (10i) linked requirements that the tool accomplishes / provides, in line with Activity 2; (iv) Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); (v) information and guides on how to install, run and access the code; and (vi) its roadmap within the project’s lifetime.

1.2. Scope of this deliverable

This deliverable reports on the software tools developed within the scope of Task 3.3 “*Software tools for multi-platform delivery and reception*”, addressed within Activity 3 “*Tools for Immersive Media Production*” of the ViVIM project. Section 2 briefly introduces the reported tools and links them with: (i) the end-to-end ViVIM platform architecture; (10) the envisioned pilots and scenarios; (10i) the contents to be produced, reported in LL2.1 [1]; and (iv) the derived requirements reported in LL2.2 [2]. Then, a Section for each of the reported tools is added. Finally, Section 8 reports on conclusions and future work directions.

1.3. Status of this deliverable

This is the first version of the deliverable LL3.3, envisioned by M15. It is delivered with a slight delay in order to report on comprehensive and functional versions of all key tools developed within T3.3. However, some of the tools have been already used in already executed pilot actions of the project, like the experiment on holo-conferencing and the Pilot 1.A, both reported in LL4.1 [1], as well as the Pilot 1.B.

A second and a third final versions of the deliverable will be provided in months M22 and M33, respectively, according to the approved workplan including a slight re-scheduling and extension of the project.

1.4. Relationship with other ViVIM activities

This is a deliverable from Activity 3 – Task 3.3, and it is highly related with other following deliverables and associated activities:

- LL2.1 [2] (Activity 2): Content Modalities and Examples to be considered for experimentation and pilot actions.
- LL2.2 [3] (Activity 2): Selected scenarios, use cases and requirements in the project. These selections will determine the tools to be developed and their required features and KPIs to be accomplished / provided within Activity 3.
- LL2.3 [4] (Activity 2): it details the production and evaluation plans, which will make use of the presented tools in this deliverable.

- LL3.1 [5] (Activity 3): the transmission and reception tools and features from this deliverable (Task 3.3) can be used to integrate the Monocular3DMaps tool from Task 3.1 in real-time end-to-end pipelines.

Likewise, this deliverable is also related with Activity 4 deliverables, like the delivered LL4.1 [1], as it reports on tools to be adopted and evaluated in the envisioned pilot actions in the project.

2. Overview of tools and their integration with ViVIM architecture

2.1. Overview of Tools and Integration within ViVIM Architecture

This deliverable reports on five different software tools being developed and/or optimized in ViVIM to provide support for all envisioned scenarios and pilot actions in the project, reported in LL2.2 [3] and LL2.3 [4]. Next, the tools reported in this deliverable are briefly introduced:

- **Multi-format 2D/360 Video Editing Plugin for Adobe Premiere Pro** (Section 3): editing and storytelling tool for multi-format and multi-screen experiences. It is a plugin of Adobe Premier Pro that has been re-lived from the H2020 ImmersiaTV project¹ (coordinated by i2CAT), updated and adapted to be used in ViVIM. The plugin allows defining interactive and personalized multi-format (2D video, 360° video, images...) and multi-screen experiences, based on users' preferences and available devices. It is mainly targeted for Content-on-Demand (CoD) scenarios, although it can be also useful for live scenarios.
- **Cloud-based Orchestrator** (Section 4): cloud-based Orchestrator adopted from the H2020 VR-Together project² (coordinated by i2CAT), updated and adapted for its dynamic virtualization and instantiation in the cloud, by using Amazon Web Services (AWS) instances. This tool is used to create and manage shared multi-user holo-portation sessions, being also responsible for managing session updates and acting as stream relay.
- **Low-latency DASH pipeline** (Section 5): newly developed Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) pipeline to carry out traditional and immersive video content with low-latency and guaranteeing in-sync stream switching between different ingests (e.g., camera views) connected to the pipeline.
- **Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline** (Section 6): newly developed pipeline to carry out and process (encode, decode) RGB-D streams captured by off-the-shelf RGB-D sensors (e.g., Azure Kinect), to be used in the envisioned holo-portation scenarios in the project.
- **WebRTC Remote Rendering Plugin** (Section 7): newly developed remote rendering plugin based on Web Real-Time Communication (WebRTC) technology and standard to allow delivering a rendered 2D stream from a Unity instance (processing multi-format formats, including 3D and volumetric content) to lightweight 2D web players. This allows increasing the scalability and interoperability of the envisioned holo-portation scenarios in the project.

Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of how each of these tools are integrated within the end-to-end ViVIM platform architecture, reported in LL2.2 [3]. More detailed architectural diagrams for each software tools are provided in the respective sections where they are presented.

Functional versions of all reported tools are available at the time of writing, although their development and refinement processes will continue in the upcoming months.

¹ ImmersiaTV project, <https://www.immersiatv.eu/> Last Access in December 2021

² VR-Together project, <https://vrtogether.eu/> Last Access in December 2021

Figure 1: High-level overview of the ViVIM architecture, integrating Task 3.3 tools

2.2. Links between tools and associated Requirements and Pilot Actions

The requirements associated to the considered content modalities and formats, as well as to the envisioned use cases and scenarios are reported in LL2.2 [3]. Table 1 lists all gathered requirements that are somehow related to the tools being developed within Task 3.3 and reported in this deliverable.

Id.	Component	Descripció	Prioritat	Responsable
FR01	Plataforma (Editing Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha d'implementar un sistema de producció i consum audiovisual centrat en una nova forma de narració audiovisual que combini formats tradicionals, omnidireccionals (360°) i de Realitat Virtual 3D, sent compatible amb els llenguatges audiovisuals clàssics (pla/contrapla, càmera lenta, etc)	MUST	i2CAT
FR02	Plataforma (Editing Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de suportar la producció mitjançant càmeres omnidireccionals i per a pantalles immersives	MUST	CCMA, VISION
FR03	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de suportar l'accés al contingut de forma coordinada, tant emprant dispositius de realitat virtual (head mounted displays, HMDs) com dispositius tradicionals (tauletes, televisió...), en entorns multi-plataforma	MUST	i2CAT
FR04	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator)	Es requereix un nou llenguatge cinematogràfic (sistema de producció, modalitats d'interacció, i model de metadades) que permeti explotar les possibilitats de la varietat de formats audiovisuals, escenaris i dispositius de consum contemplats al projecte	MUST	CCMA, VISION

FR05	Plataforma (Editing Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de suportar la definició de portal dinàmics i interactius que possibilitin la inserció de seqüències audiovisual o elements multimèdia addicionals, seguint una narrativa especificada en procés de producció, i que permeti experiències més interactives i personalitzades	MUST	VISYON
FR06	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de permetre la producció i distribució de continguts en diferit	MUST	CCMA
FR07	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline, Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de permetre la producció i distribució de continguts en viu	MUST	CCMA
NF08	Plataforma (Orchestrator, DASH Pipeline, Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	El retard extrem-a-extrem per a continguts en viu deu proporcionar una experiència d'usuari satisfactòria, permeten un nivells de sincronització i interacció acceptables	MUST	CCMA, I2CAT
FR09	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de possibilitar experiències multimèdia personalitzades, en funció de les possibilitats de selecció de continguts i dispositius de consum, així com modalitats d'interacció	MUST	CCMA
FR10	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator, DASH Pipeline)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de possibilitar experiències multimèdia lineals, en les que els temps i l'ordre de les escenes estarà prefixat en la fase de producció, encara que l'usuari pugui explorar lliurement les escenes 360°	MUST	CCMA, VISYON
FR11	Plataforma (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de possibilitar experiències multimèdia en mode exploració, en les que l'usuari podrà navegar a través d'escenes, afectar el seu ordre així com els temps dels esdeveniments mostrats, en base a la seva activitat i interaccions	MUST	CCMA, VISYON
FR12	Plataforma (DASH Pipeline, Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma ViVIM ha de suportar solucions de streaming adaptades als continguts i escenaris del projecte, tenint en compte els camps de visió instantanis dels usuaris, i els recursos de xarxa disponibles	MUST	CCMA, I2CAT
FR13	Producció (Editing Plugin)	La producció de continguts ha d'incloure i integrar fluxos de vídeos tradicionals, omnidireccionals, gràfics interactius i elements 3D, creant una trama narrativa interactiva i	MUST	CCMA, EURECAT, VISYON

		immersiva		
FR15	Producció (Editing Plugin, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La producció de continguts s'ha d'adequar als diferents tipus de dispositius de consum contemplats al projecte, evitant problemes de compatibilitat	MUST	CCMA, EURECAT, VISYON
FR17	Producció (Editing Plugin)	La producció multi-format deu possibilitar una integració i composició natural i realista de les diferents tipologies de continguts	MUST	CCMA, EURECAT, VISYON
FR18	Producció (Editing Plugin)	La incorporació de grafismes i elements interactius s'ha d'adaptar a les especificitats de les tipologies de continguts considerades (plànols esfèrics, escenes 3D...)	MUST	CCMA, EURECAT, VISYON
FR19	Producció (Editing Plugin)	Els continguts a produir han de permetre unes narratives interactives adaptades als entorns multi-format i multi-dispositiu contemplats al projecte	SHOULD	CCMA, VISYON, CVC, EURECAT
FR20	Producció (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline)	Els continguts a produir han de captar l'atenció cap a uns punts claus, per tal de possibilitar i estimular la interacció.	SHOULD	CCMA, VISYON
FR21	Post-Producció (Editing Plugin)	La plataforma ha d'incloure un conjunt d'eines de producció (e.g. "plugins" compatibles amb eines existents, com Adobe Premier Pro) que permeten l'edició i post-producció d'experiències audiovisuals multi-plataforma.	MUST	CVC, EURECAT
FR25	Producció (Editing Plugin)	Els mecanismes de tracking deuen possibilitar la inserció dinàmica d'elements audiovisuals addicionals, així com nous mecanismes d'interacció	SHOULD	CVC, VISYON, i2CAT
FR29	Reproductor (DASH Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	El reproductor ViVIM ha de ser multi-plataforma i capaç de reproduir els continguts en dispositius de Realitat Virtual (e.x. HMDs) i tradicionals (e.x. tauletes i televisió)	MUST	I2CAT
FR30	Reproductor (DASH Pipeline)	El reproductor ViVIM ha de permetre a l'usuari navegar lliurement entre les escenes omnidireccionals, tant en dispositius de Realitat Virtual (giroscopi, controladors...), com en dispositius tradicionals (teclat, ratolí...)	MUST	I2CAT
FR32	Reproductor (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator)	El reproductor ViVIM ha de ser capaç de sol·licitar, rebre, reproduir i integrar les diferents tipologies de continguts que conformen una experiència multimèdia	MUST	I2CAT
FR34	Reproductor (Editing Plugin, Orchestrator, Remote Rendering Plugin)	La plataforma deu permetre el accés als continguts, o part d'ells, a usuaris que utilitzen dispositius tradicionals, alhora que altres usuaris utilitzen dispositius de Realitat Virtual	SHOULD	I2CAT, VISYON360, CCMA

FR35	Reproductor (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	El reproductor ha de suportar mecanismes d'interacció passiva amb el contingut (per exemple, si un usuari mira a un element concret de l'escena, començarà una acció concreta).	MUST	I2CAT, VISYON360, CCMA
FR36	Reproductor (Editing Plugin, DASH Pipeline, Remote Rendering Plugin)	El reproductor ha de suportar mecanismes d'interacció activa amb els contingut (per exemple: l'usuari interactua de forma activa amb un element virtual de l'escena).	MUST	I2CAT, VISYON360, CCMA
FR44	Plataforma (Orchestrator)	La plataforma ViViM deu incloure un model de metadades per al catàleg de continguts del pilot 1, així com una API per a la integració dels continguts a l'entorn virtual 3D	MUST	CCMA

Table 1: List of requirements associated to the T3.3 tools (text in Catalan, as extracted from LL2.1 [3])

Table 2 maps the reported tools with pilot actions considered in the ViViM project.

Tool	Pilot Actions
Multi-format 2D/360 Video Editing Plugin for Adobe Premier Pro	Testing the tool with professional user. If successful, adoption of such a tool in posterior VR360-related pilot actions
Cloud-based Orchestrator	Holo-rotation based pilot actions and demonstrators
Low-latency DASH pipeline	All VR360-related pilot actions in the project
Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline	Experiment to compare performance and visual quality of this pipeline compared to the Point Cloud pipeline used in the holo-conferencing experiment reported in LL4.1 [1]. If successful, adoption of such a tool in posterior pilot actions involving holo-rotation.
WebRTC Remote Rendering Plugin	Experiment to assess performance, robustness and perceived quality when using such a tool. If successful, adoption of such a tool in posterior pilot actions involving holo-rotation, especially those involving scalability features and in demonstration actions.

Table 2: List of requirements associated to the T3.3 tools (text in Catalan, as extracted from LL2.2)

3. Multi-format 2D/360 Video Editing Plugin

3.1. Brief Introduction to the Component / Tool

This tool is an Adobe Premiere Pro extension that provides three new add-ons for enabling video editing of interactive experiences, combining multi-format 2D and 360° video assets, to be played out in single- and multi-screen scenarios, and using both traditional and Virtual Reality (VR) displays. The new add-ons include: (i) two video effects; (10) one pack of transitions for immersive content elements; and (10i) one extension panel that allows to configure a set of parameters, add interactive elements, and finally export the edited project using standard-compliant metadata to be processed by an associated media player.

This is a tool developed in the EU H2020 ImmersiaTV project, reported in D3.3 of that precedent project [6], that has been updated and adapted for its adoption in ViVIM.

3.2. State-of-the-art and Provided Innovations / Benefits

The tool was designed and developed to fill gaps in other existing tools, as analyzed in D2.2 of ImmersiaTV [7], delivered in 2018, by providing the three key innovative features mentioned in the previous subsections, which are detailed in next subsections.

Within ViVIM, this software tool has been recovered and updated from ImmersiaTV for its adoption in the envisioned pilot actions, by including some potential adaptations and refinements. Both the plugin and player have been updated and tested to become compliant with the latest 2021 versions of Adobe Premiere Pro and associated encoding tools.

Specifically, it has been necessary to adapt functions to enable generation and exportation of all the content created by the plugin, including both a metadata file to be interpreted by the media player and the processing of the videos through the associated Adobe Media Encoder tool, which has also undergone various modifications since 2017. Other key updates have been performed and applied to many libraries associated with Node.js³, a server incorporated into the plugin to be able to provide a preview mode to professional users of the tool. In addition, after some performance and validation tests, some implementation details have been refined to improve the performance and robustness of the tool.

3.3. Architecture

This tool is a plugin / extension of Adobe Premiere Pro, and thus used within the Content Preparation block of the ViVIM platform (Figure 1). The content and metadata it generates are made available to web players via a web / content server.

More details about its architecture and implementation can be found in D3.3 of ImmersiaTV [6].

3.4. Components and APIs

This subsection describes the different features / extensions that the tool provides, and how they are provided.

³ Node.js, <https://nodejs.org/en/> Last Access in December 2021

3.4.1 Video Effects

This extension adds an extra package with two video effects into the *Effects panel*, under the (*ImmersiaTV / ViVIM*) plugin folder. The usage of both effects is exactly the same as that when using other effects from Adobe Premiere Pro: the user only needs to drag and drop the effect over the desired clip and control its parameters through the *Effect controls* panel.

3.4.1.1. 360 projection mapping

The base of an immersive omnidirectional scene is a 360° video, but there are different options to represent that content modality in a 2D space. The most common format is the equirectangular projection (Figure 2), as it is very intuitive. However, it is not the optimal representation format in terms of encoding / processing, because distortion is added on the poles in the transformation from a sphere to a plain, adding also pixel redundancy. Other representation formats, like cubic (Figure 3) or pyramidal, become more efficient in terms of processing, but more challenging to visually interpret while editing.

Natively, Adobe Premiere Pro only natively supports equirectangular projection. However, a new plugin effect *360 Projection Mapping* has been developed to provide support for cubic projection. This new effect additionally performs a real time transformation from cubic to equirectangular projection to preview the video in Adobe Premiere Pro in a more understandable / intuitive way.

It also allows useful adjustments in the horizontal and vertical offsets to correct directions in the 3D space. By playing with these parameters, the producer can select the point of interest (Figure 3), and also modify or correct the camera calibration (e.g. due to a bad positioning on the capture process).

Figure 2: Illustration of Equirectangular projection (applying 360 projection Mapping to a cubic input)

Figure 3: Illustration of Cubemap projection input with 360 projection Mapping deactivated

3.4.1.2. Portals

This is a new effect that allows the content creator to introduce interactive elements and features. In particular, the effect allows adding a dynamic video insert, which allows viewers to influence the displayed content (e.g., show/hide elements, switch between views). It can be a rectangular insert from a directional camera or a static graphic (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Directive graphic with Portal effect deactivated

Portals can be inserts on the 3D world (*World reference*), meaning they stay always in the same 3D (x,y,z) coordinates, or they can be overlaid on the screen (*User reference*).

A world reference portal can be positioned everywhere on the 3D scene, always looking at the camera. Its position is based on XYZ spherical coordinates mapped on a 2D preview, being (0,0) the center of the 2D composition. X means the radius or distance to center, Y azimuth and Z elevation or inclination, where the last two magnitudes are expressed in angle degrees. *Vertical position* allows values on the range (-90,90), while *Horizontal position* on the range (-180,180) to cover all the range of the sphere. The distance position (Z) is computed depending on the track position on the sequence, as explained next.

User reference portals (Figure 5) are positioned in a 2D space because they are overlaid on the screen. As screen sizes can be different on each device, relative values for their position on the screen are used. These values are percentages, being (0,0) the upper-left corner and (100,100) the lower-right corner.

Figure 5: Directive graphic with Portal effect activated and set as User reference

The editor (i.e. professional user) can define its size, position and visibility using the *Effect Controls* panel, and it can also define some interactions between elements, using the *onActionStart* field and selecting the target element. That way, by clicking on this portal, i.e., pressing it on a tablet or staring at it on a Head Mounted Display (HMD), the player can for instance show or hide another element on the scene.

Typically, Adobe Premiere Pro tracks act like compositing layers, where top layers cover the ones at their back. Therefore, the tracks on the bottom must be the omnidirectional videos, then the world reference portals must be added, and finally the user reference ones. We use this layer-based concept to generate the export metadata, using the tracks position and type to compute distances and avoid collisions between elements. With this purpose, three distance zones have been defined: (i) User reference portals are located at distance 0.3 from the camera and always follow its position; (10) World reference portals are located between 0.31 and 0.8 and are static in the 3D world; and (10i) 360 videos from 0.81 to 1.

This effect is integrated within the Adobe Premiere Pro built-in preview, which eases the fine-tuning of multi-device experiences. Premiere Pro also includes an internal VR preview where the user can navigate across the 360 scene. The problem with it is that the VR preview is a 2D projection of the scene, so it is suitable for *World reference* portals, but not for *User reference* portals because they are treated as a world reference ones and do not follow the camera (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Examples of Differences between a User portal on native Pro VR preview (left) and on the developed custom preview (right)

3.4.2. Transitions

For smooth opening and closing of *Portals*, as well as switching between omnidirectional videos, a set of basic transitions compatible with the associated 360° player (Task 3.4) was implemented.

These transitions are Dissolve, Iris Open/Close, Wipe Open/Close and Wipe Left/Right:

- Dissolve: The dissolve transition gradually mixes one scene into another. Figure 8 shows an example of this transition applied between two clips.

Figure 7: Dissolve transition

- Iris Open/Close: The iris transition reproduces the effect of opening (Iris Open) or closing (Iris Close) the iris of a camera lens.

Figure 8: Iris Open transition

- Wipe Open/Close: The wipe effect replaces one scene to another moving the preceding scene out of the way. In wipe open, that effect starts in the center of screen (Figure 9), and in wipe close this effect starts on the two lateral sides of the screen.

Figure 9: Wipe Open transition

- Wipe Left/Right: In a wipe left, the effect starts on the left side of screen, as shown in Figure 10, and in a wipe right the transition effect starts on the right side of screen.

Figure 10: Wipe Left transition

3.4.3. Export Panel

This panel is the most important piece of the extension, because it generates data that allows the understanding between the production and delivery modules (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Export Panel

The export panel lists all the video tracks on the active sequence and allows users to select their type (directive/spherical) and target devices (HMD/Tablet/TV). It extends the standard Adobe Premiere Pro editing process, in which video tracks are generally mixed together in a sequence, to edit videos in a common sequence but targeting different devices for media presentation. With this approach it is possible to assign a single track to be rendered on different devices, but to keep a common timeline for all of them, thus without the need for creating a new sequence for each device, making it easier and keep an in-sync presentation of all associated media elements. The aim is to mix omnidirectional, traditional video footage and images into an appealing multi-device end user experience.

The panel also enables an efficient project export procedure to a suitable format (media files and metadata) that represents the multi-device content. This format is used for delivery and

multi-device audience consumption. It is possible to define the output quality (resolution and bitrate) for spherical and directive (TV) videos, while a fixed low resolution (426x240) is typically used for the portals given their reduced size on the scene. After defining these parameters, all the tracks are rendered with a single click on the *Export* button, which also includes the generation of the associated metadata.

3.4.3.1. Custom Preview

The panel also includes a custom external preview, for a static check of the composition status in the associated 360° player. While previewing, the user reference portals are attached to the screen, unlike the fixed 3D world in the Adobe Premiere Pro VR preview, and the interactivity between elements on the same sequence can be tested to some extent.

By clicking the *Preview* button, a QR code (Figure 12) is generated and displayed in the *Export* panel. That QR code allows directly previewing the composition on mobile devices, by scanning it.

Figure 12: Example of QR code generated for external preview

3.5. Requirements & Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The system / processing requirements for using this tool are the same as for using Adobe Premiere Pro: <https://helpx.adobe.com/premiere-pro/system-requirements.html> However, it is important to note that the tool has been designed for editing high-quality immersive media elements, which increase the processing requirements.

The plugin has been developed to be run on Windows machines.

No performance and scalability KPIs are provided for this tool in this version of the deliverable.

3.6. Integration Status

The plugin has been successfully installed and tested on different Windows desktops and laptops. In addition, it has been tested that the produced content and metadata have been correctly interpreted and presented on the web-based 360° player, running on different types of devices: mobile, PCs, HMDs, etc.

Concrete pilot actions for this tool will shed more light on its adequate performance and behaviour when using other types of devices.

3.7. Distribution Model

The exact distribution model for the updated version of this tool still needs to be assessed, and will be indicated in a future version of this deliverable.

3.8. Installation, Setup and Usage Guides

3.8.1. Access to the Code

The code of this Adobe Premier Pro plugin is available at the Bitbucket repository of i2CAT:
<https://bitbucket.i2cat.net/projects/IMTV/repos/immersiatv-adobe-plugin/browse>

Credentials to access and download it can be given, if requested to mia.support@i2cat.net or to the project's coordinator sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

3.8.2. Installation and Setup

The software package comes with a user-friendly Windows-style installation process. The resources and process are detailed in Annex 10.

3.8.3. Tool Usage

Annex 10 provides a guide on how to install and use that tool, providing some illustrative examples of its possibilities.

3.8.4. Access to the Online Version of the Tool

Not applicable. It is a native application / plugin to be installed on a Windows machine

4. Tool 2: Cloud-based Orchestrator

4.1. Brief Introduction to the Component / Tool

This tool consists of an Orchestrator adopted from the EU H2020 VR-Together project to support the envisioned pilot actions in ViVIM, while also adding key optimizations to such a software component.

Commonly, Orchestration software components (i.e. Orchestrators) are used in video-conferencing systems to handle the set of audiovisual and control streams [8, 9]. In ViVIM, the Orchestrator from VR-Together has been adopted to perform the following key actions to support the envisioned multi-party social scenarios: (i) handle remote networking information (e.g., IP addresses, ports, protocols); (ii) deal with session management tasks (e.g. selection of user's representation formats, scenario, session lifetime, etc.); (iii) accommodate all remote users in a shared virtual environment / session; (iv) manage real-time interaction channels, acting as a relay server for media streams; (v) exchange the users' positions in a 3D environment; (vi) ensure a consistent synchronized experience, including event notifications; etc. In addition, the Orchestrator informs about potential errors or unexpected behaviors in the distributed shared sessions, and could potentially perform a set of recovery actions in case of connection problems.

Apart from adapting the Orchestrator from VR-Together to the newly considered use cases and scenarios in ViVIM, this tool has been significantly evolved and adapted for its dynamic virtualization and instantiation on the cloud, by using AWS. That way, new instances of the Orchestrator can be easily launched on demand, based on specific needs.

4.2. State-of-the-art and Provided Innovations / Benefits

Orchestration components have been widely developed and adopted for multi-user multimedia sessions, like video conferencing (e.g. [8, 9]) and social viewing tools (e.g. [10]). However, Orchestration components for multi-party holo-portation services are not yet commonplace, apart from the one developed within VR-Together project [11, 12], adopted and optimized in ViVIM for its dynamic virtualization and instantiation in the cloud.

4.1. Architecture

The integration of the Orchestrator within the end-to-end ViVIM architecture is shown in Figure 1. Prior to creating or joining a session, the clients need to get connected to the Orchestrator and configure some settings (e.g., delivery protocols, user's representation format, microphone, camera(s), scene, etc.). Once the session is created, the clients exchange metadata and control information with / through the Orchestrator. The Orchestrator also includes a Selective Forwarding Unit (SFU) component, called Evanescent, for media relay. In this case, the media being forwarded corresponds to the users' representations in the established multi-party holo-portation scenarios.

The Orchestrator software component has been prepared as a dockerfile and can be transferred as a cloud Amazon Machine Image (AMI). That eases replication and scalability. The Evanescent subcomponent is also prepared as a dockerfile, included in the same AMI as the Orchestrator. The usage of AMI instead of docker is advised to ease exploitation opportunities, as dockerization implies some manual configuration and upgrades, which should be avoided as much as possible. The goal in ViVIM is to adapt and prepare the architectural design (including virtualization and cloud management) of the Orchestrator such that the chances of technology transfer and exploitation are maximized.

4.2. Components and APIs

As mentioned, the evolved version of the Orchestrator from ViVIM is provided as an AMI that can be instantiated on demand on AWS. Two main software components can be differentiated: Orchestration / Session management, and SFU-Evanescent.

More details about its architectural aspects (4.3) as well as about its software sub-components, modules and APIs are provided in D3.8 of VR-Together project [13].

In essence, the Orchestrator provides APIs to perform the following key features:

- (i) handle the remote networking information (e.g., IP addresses, ports, protocols) to the participating entities in holo-portation sessions;
- (10) deal with session setup (e.g., selection of user's representation formats, scenario, selection of mic / cameras, etc.) and management (e.g., create, join, leave, destroy, etc.) tasks;
- (10i) accommodate all remote users in a shared virtual environment / session;
- (iv) manage the real-time interaction channels, acting as a relay server for media streams;
- (v) exchange the users' positions in the 3D environment;
- (vi) ensure a consistent synchronized experience, including event notifications; etc.

In addition, the Orchestrator informs about potential errors or unexpected behaviors in the distributed shared sessions and could potentially perform a set of recovery actions in case of connection problems. Future versions of the deliverable will further elaborate on this.

4.3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

4.5.1. System / Processing Requirements

The cloud Orchestrator has been deployed on an Amazon EC2 T2 Instance⁴, which is a general-purpose instance type that provides the ability to burst above baseline when needed. The associated system requirements are: 2 cores and 4 GB RAM.

4.5.2. Performance / Scalability KPIs

Different tests have been carried out to assess the performance, resources usage and scalability constraints when using the Orchestrator in different types of multi-user sessions, also addressing concurrency of sessions.

Unfortunately, these tests have not been automated (yet), so therefore we did neither run many iterations nor report on a wide set of test conditions. However, we believe the conducted tests are sufficient to ensure that the Orchestrator performs very satisfactorily, in a stable and robust manner, not being a bottleneck in such types of sessions. Moreover, an evolved version of the Orchestrator is planned within ViVIM to deal with both a larger number of users per session and with horizontal scalability.

These tests reported on CPU, GPU and RAM usage, measured on both the Orchestrator and one client. The measurement tools included: *tshark*⁵, *htop*⁶ Linux shell toolkit on the Orchestrator, and the tool from [14] (based on the use of the Windows *Powershell*⁷).

⁴ <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/instance-types/t2/> Last Access in December 2021

⁵ <https://www.wireshark.org/docs/man-pages/tshark.html> Last Access in December 2021

⁶ <https://htop.dev/> Last Access in December 2021

⁷ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/powershell/> Last Access in December 2021

The considered test conditions included:

- Session with 1 single Point Cloud + 1 spectator (no audio, no video)
- Session with 2 single Point Cloud users
- Session with 4 single Point Cloud users
- Session with 6 single Point Cloud users
- Session with 1 Webcam + 1 single Point Cloud user
- Session with 2 Webcam + 2 single Point Cloud users
- 3 sessions with 2 webcam users
- 4 sessions with 2 webcam users
- 3 sessions with 2 single Point Cloud users
- 4 sessions with 2 single Point Cloud users

Note that the Point Cloud representation could be from either a synthetic Point Cloud or from a real-time captured user, but with the same magnitude of points and frames per second (fps). The duration for each test was 5 minutes. The obtained results can be found here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/165Jn1J1rSpk5Bty4Ld75_Qr2o3kG_QL5?usp=sharing. These results, or other ones from similar tests, will be analyzed with more details in deliverables from Activity 4.

4.4. Integration Status

Both the native and virtualizable versions of the Orchestrator have been successfully integrated within the ViVIM platform architecture. Indeed, the connection and interaction processes with the Orchestrator are being packaged and prepared as a Software as a Service (SaaS). The complete list of methods and APIs used in the client to get connected and interact with the Orchestrator are reported in LL3.4 [15].

Likewise, the Orchestrator is expected to be evolved within the ViVIM's lifetime to be included in a service-oriented cloud architecture, with decoupled and modular features and services. Such planned features will be described in a future version of this deliverable.

4.5. Distribution Model

The exact distribution model for the updated version of this tool still needs to be assessed, and will be indicated in a future version of this deliverable.

4.6. Installation, Setup and Usage Guides

4.8.1. Access to the Code

The code of this Adobe Premier Pro plugin is available at the Bitbucket repository of i2CAT: <https://bitbucket.i2cat.net/projects/VIVIM/repos/vrt-orchestrator/browse>

Credentials to access and download it can be given, if requested, to mia.support@i2cat.net or to the project's coordinator sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

4.8.2. Installation and Setup

In order to virtualize orchestrator and SFU components we have used two approaches. One of them consists of using a docker container for the Orchestrator and SFU (included in the code). The other one consists of deploying the Orchestrator and SFU in a EC2 server Ubuntu

20.04. SFU has several dependencies, which needs a manual symbolic link in the operative system and we are using the binary. Both were the reason to avoid docker: in this case the technical transference would be difficult and requires maintenance tasks to update the Ubuntu base image which uses docker.

The Orchestrator has an easier set-up, running a script to set-up samples as user and scenarios database and communication with SFU configuration. Once edited the config file (IP, port) and setting up the firewall rules so that client can connect via socket.io with the orchestrator. The config file (IP, port) and the firewall rules have to be configured first in order to establish connection between the client and Orchestrator via socket.io. The Orchestrator dockerfile is already optimized and was used to apply continuous integration strategy to automate the build check when adding any modification.

The instance allows to monitor metrics, to scale resources with fast application and to create an AMI image in one click. In this way, adapting the instance to the use-case requirements, creating the adapted image and transferring it becomes a simplified process. We can provide a way to install an instance in another AWS server easily.

The next figures provide screenshots of an Amazon EC2 t2.medium instance on which the Orchestrator is running

Figure 13: Orchestrator running on an Amazon EC2 t2.medium instance

Figure 14: Examples of Metrics collected from the cloud-based Orchestrator

4.8.3. Tool Usage

The complete list of methods and APIs used in the client to get connected and interact with the Orchestrator are reported in LL3.4 [15].

4.8.4. Access to the Online Version of the Tool

An online version of the Orchestrator is available in an online server (IP: 54.78.26.205).

The port to be used to communicate the clients and the Orchestrator, via Socket.io, is configured in the clients (reported in LL3.4), and in the associated server instance, by also configuring the firewall to permit the associated traffic.

5. Tool 3: Low-latency HAS / DASH pipeline

5.1. Brief Introduction to the Component / Tool

ViVIM addresses the distribution of live and on-demand content over heterogeneous and multi-platform scenarios. In this context, HTTP Adaptive Streaming (HAS) technologies, like Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) and HTTP Live Streaming (HLS), have become dominant.

The project is devoting efforts in this context with the goal of leveraging the potential of such technologies in terms of adaptability, ubiquity and scalability, but also increasing their capabilities in terms of interaction, while minimizing end-to-end delays. In this context, advanced encoding, signaling, delivery and synchronization methods are being developed and integrated into an end-to-end pipeline. This pipeline allows a low-latency distribution of immersive and traditional content, via DASH and HLS, including the parallel encoding and unified signaling of multiple parallel video ingests. It also allows (dynamically) concentrating the video resolution on the user's viewport by adopting different strategies.

5.2. State-of-the-art and Provided Innovations / Benefits

In the last few years, the scientific community and industry have devoted significant efforts to optimizing the performance and Quality of Experience (QoE) of VR360 video services, both considering Content on Demand (CoD) and live scenarios, as surveyed and analyzed in [15] and [16]. Examples of innovative contributions in this area rely on increasing the video resolution, minimizing latency and enabling viewport-aware VR360 video solutions.

ViVIM also targets these objectives, but the goal is still to exploit the advantages of HAS technology and to provide simple, yet effective, viewport-aware VR360 services, using traditional and web-compliant codecs (e.g. H264), thus guaranteeing compatibility with web clients. Likewise, the targeted solution aims at involving just one single media stream, without requiring many decoding instances and synchronization solutions at the client side.

In addition, precedent works have already provided technological contributions to enable multi-view VR360 scenarios (e.g., [17]). However, they were not efficient in terms of scalability and interactive responsiveness, and required ad-hoc extensions to existing standard solutions (e.g., DASH). ViVIM aims at overcoming these limitations through the presented pipeline and associated web player (contribution from Task 3.4, reported in LL3.4).

5.3. Architecture

The developed pipeline adopts a classical server-client architecture as for current-day HAS services. Its integration within the end-to-end ViVIM architecture is shown in Figure 1. In particular, the pipeline connects media capturing sources with web clients via a web server for live services, and is used to delivery stored content from web servers to remote clients for CoD services.

A few particular aspects about its architecture can be highlighted though:

- The pipeline supports the parallel ingest of video streams from different cameras / sources, being delivered via IP protocols (e.g., Real Time Messaging Protocol (RTMP) or Real Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP)) or via an High Definition Multimedia Interface (HDMI) (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Example of end-to-end video pipeline, including the ingest of multiple sources, encoding and delivery steps

- The pipeline allows the establishment of a bidirectional channel between the encoding engine and the media players, so that each media player can periodically report on the current viewport (i.e. the region of the 360° being watched at the moment, determined by the size of the Field of View (FoV) of the employed device) to adjust the encoding process with the goal of maximizing the video resolution in that region (Figure 16), while minimizing the bandwidth consumption. For such a purpose, a *ffmpeg*⁸ video filter, called *addroi*⁹, has been adopted and adapted to enable its dynamic adjustment during a streaming session.

Figure 16: Overview of the viewport aware processing pipeline for VR360 video (in Equirectangular Projection (ERP))

- As the previous viewport-aware solution requires one stream per (each active) client, an independent viewport-aware encoding process can be instantiated for each client requiring this feature (Figure 17), thus creating a new viewport processing branch per client, e.g. by relying on *ffmpeg pipe tees*¹⁰. This, of course, brings scalability issues that will be explored in the third year of the project.

Figure 17: Multi-output pipeline to generate a personalized viewport-aware stream per connected client

⁸ *ffmpeg*, <https://www.ffmpeg.org/> Last Access in December 2021

⁹ *addroi* filter, <https://ffmpeg.org/ffmpeg-filters.html#addroi> Last Access in December 2021

¹⁰ *Ffmpeg pipe tees*, <https://trac.ffmpeg.org/wiki/Creating%20multiple%20outputs> Last Access in December 2021

5.4. Components and APIs

1. The pipeline allows multiple types of ingests, including: live sources delivered via IP protocols (e.g., RTMP, RTSP), as well as via SDI and HDMI interfaces, and CoD from a given server / repository.

2. The pipeline supports both traditional ERP projections, which is the format provided by most state-of-the-art 360° cameras, and Cubemap Projection (CMP), as well as a dynamic transformation between both representation formats.

3. The pipeline supports viewport-aware processing (encoding and delivery) to concentrate the resolution on specific regions (e.g. viewport), based both on static and dynamic settings:

3.1. Static Non-Uniform CMP Strategies: The cube can be strategically composed and encoded such that different resolutions are assigned to each of the faces (or other defined regions of the 360° scene). This encoding setting is kept throughout the duration of the video clip or media session.

Figure 18 provides some examples of the state-of-the-art uniform CMP strategy (left) together with the two proposed non-uniform CMP strategies with different resolutions for the different faces, in this case concentrating the resolution on the horizontal panorama (center) and frontal face (right).

With these non-uniform encoding and composition settings we allow for up to 30% bandwidth savings, without degrading the Quality of Experience (QoE) and just requiring minor adaptations to a traditional 360° media player (just metadata on how to compose the cube).

Figure 18: Examples of uniform and non-uniform encoding using CMP

3.2. Dynamic Non-Uniform CMP Strategies: The above proposals are promising, but do not allow for dynamically changing the resolutions for different parts of the 360° scene based on the consumers' viewing patterns. Accordingly, new optimization strategies have been devised to be able to provide N different versions of the 360° video stream, allowing their dynamic selection by the 360° player (e.g., 6 versions of a cube, concentrating the resolution on each of its faces) based on the user's viewing patterns. In such a case, each one of the versions of the cube are provided via a different video track signaled within the same Media Presentation Description (MPD) of the DASH session as a different *AdaptationSet* [18].

An online demo for a video with 6 versions of a cube concentrating the resolution on each one of its faces can be watched at: <https://media.i2cat.net/Respond-A/v2/#0>. In the presented video, the acronym of the selected face with high resolution is overlaid for clarity purposes. This is a proof of concept to illustrate this promising feature. The demo will be evolved to optimize the switching process between faces, both in terms of smoothness and rapid switching, in future versions of the deliverable.

With these improvements, the previously discussed bandwidth savings in step 3.1 will be kept, but the QoE is expected to improve (tests to be conducted soon within the project).

3.3. Viewport-aware ERP processing: as detailed in Section 5.3.

4. Parallel encoding of multiple input sources: in case that multiple sources are ingested in parallel, via whatever delivery channel, they are linked with different inputs parameters (-i) of the ffmpeg program / script, and encoded within the same ffmpeg instance. That way, the same clock reference is used to assign timestamps to each one of the inputs, and all of them are encoded and packaged using exactly the same settings and machine.

5. Content / Session Signaling: For each of the single- or multiple-input content being encoded and packaged, a manifest file is created to signal all available content versions for their (dynamic) selection at the player side (details in LL3.4). The signaling required to support the envisioned multi-input and viewport-aware scenarios are compliant with the DASH specification, just requiring the addition of extra *AdaptationSet* tracks and a strategic naming convention and labeling of their ids.

Interestingly, the engine supports the encoding of the input content using the latest versions of DASH Low-Latency, using Common Media Application Format (CMAF) chunks. By doing so, the same encoded content can be provided via both DASH and HLS, by creating their associated manifest files in parallel. This allows providing support for Apple / Mac devices, for which the support of DASH is limited.

6. Content transfer to the media server / Content Delivery Network (CDN): In these cases where the encoding engine (ffmpeg program) is run on a different machine than the content / web server, or CDN, to be used, the produced HAS content is transferred via conventional *push / pop* methods.

5.5. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

5.5.1. System / Processing Requirements

The associated ffmpeg scripts / programs and web servers to host and deliver the produced HAS content can be installed and run on any PC / laptop with low system / processing requirements. Obviously, the requirements become more stringent for: (i) live scenarios that require real-time processing; (ii) high-resolution input sources; (iii) many parallel input sources; (iv) multiple parallel output video streams.

Two reference tests are cited:

- An Intel 9 NUC with GPU is able to encode in real-time a live video feed with 4K resolution from a 360° video camera, using DASH Low-Latency.
- A setup with a GPU RTX 3080 and a Blackmagic Decklink Quad HDMI capture card¹¹ has shown that it is possible to encode up to 3 4K live 360° streams in parallel. That is precisely the setup used in Pilot 2.a of the project.

5.5.2. Performance / Scalability KPIs

¹¹ Blackmagic Decklink Quad HDMI capture card, <https://www.blackmagicdesign.com/products/decklink/techspecs/W-DLK-36> Last Access in December 2021

First, conducted tests have shown that the DASH Low-Latency pipeline is able to ensure end-to-end (indeed, glass-to-glass) delays shorter than 1s for live 4K 360° video streams. A demo video of a setup demonstrating is available [here](#).

Second, conducted tests have shown that the delays since reporting the player viewport and receiving the updated stream with the maximum resolution on that reported viewport are in the order of 1s. A demo video of a setup demonstrating is available [here](#).

Finally, as part of Task 3.4, the developed 360° web player is being extended with a module to register Quality of Service (QoS) / QoE-related metrics on cloud-based databases and to be visualized in near real-time on a dashboard. Once ready, evaluation tests will be conducted to determine performance / scalability KPIs for the considered use cases, in a variety of scenarios. Likewise, future development efforts will be targeted at increasing the modularity scalability of the ViVIM delivery pipeline in this context.

5.6. Integration Status

The low-latency HAS / DASH pipeline has been successfully installed and run on different Windows and Linux desktops and laptops, when using different types of media inputs. In addition, it has been tested that the produced content and metadata are correctly interpreted and presented on the web-based 360° player, when being run on different types of devices: mobile, PCs, HMDs, etc. Consequently, it is considered this tool / component has been satisfactorily integrated into the ViVIM platform.

Furthermore, the pilot actions to be conducted to test this tool will shed more light on its adequate performance and behaviour when using other types of devices, and over different scenarios.

5.7. Distribution Model

The exact distribution model for the updated version of this tool still needs to be assessed, and will be indicated in a future version of this deliverable. However, it should be noted that this pipeline has been built by mainly using ffmpeg (Lesser General Public License (LGPL)), and requires the use of a web server, like Apache (permissive free software license written by the Apache Software Foundation (ASF)), or any other open-source one.

5.8. Installation, Setup and Usage Guides

5.8.1. Access to the Code

Not applicable, but check the details provided along this subsection. Extra information can be requested to mia.support@i2cat.net or to the project's coordinator sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

5.8.2. Installation and Setup

Two key tools / resources need to be installed to run the Low-Latency DASH pipeline: 1) ffmpeg; and 2) a web server. Although these are widespread tools for the media community, their installation processes on Linux machines are detailed next:

- FFMPEG Installation:
 - `$ sudo apt update`

- `$ sudo apt install ffmpeg`

To verify the installation, use the `ffmpeg -version` command, which prints the ffmpeg version:

- `$ ffmpeg -version`

It is also possible to directly download a ffmpeg build, or to compile ffmpeg from the source code in case that any modification wants to be applied.

- NGINX installation (the process for other servers is pretty similar):
 - `$sudo apt update`
 - `$ sudo apt install nginx`
 - `$ sudo systemctl start nginx`

5.8.3. Tool Usage

Next, a relevant example script using the pipeline is provided. Note that no scripts are provided yet for pipelines involving viewport-aware processing as well as for multi-input and multi-output sources. The code for these pipelines will be fully documented in upcoming versions of this deliverable, including the consequent modifications to the `ffmpeg` code, and the lessons learned from the conducted tests (e.g., recommended settings).

- DASH Low-Latency generation using GPU encoding (CUDA):

```

ffmpeg \
-r 30 \           Set input framerate
-thread_queue_size 9999 \
-hwaccel cuda \
-hwaccel_output_format cuda \
-f rtsp \
-i rtsp://[IP]:[PORT]\
-c:v h264_nvenc \
-pix_fmt yuv420p \
-b:v 10M \       Set input video bitrate
-maxrate:v 10M \ Set input video max bitrate
-b:a 48k \
-use_timeline 0 \
-use_template 1 \
-utc_timing_url "http://time.akamai.com/?iso" \
-format_options "movflags=cmaf" \
-frag_type duration \
-adaptation_sets "id=0, seg_duration=[seconds], frag_duration=[seconds],
streams=v id=1, seg_duration=1, frag_type=none, streams=a" \
-dash_segment_type "mp4" \
-g:v [Integer] \ Set GoP value
-keyint_min:v [Integer] \ Set key frame minimum interval
-forced-idr 0 \
-sc_threshold:v 0 \
-streaming 1 \
-ldash 1 \
-tune zerolatency \
-export_side_data 1 \
-write_prft 1 \
-target_latency [seconds] \ Set target latency for player

```

```
-color_primaries bt709 -color_trc bt709 -colorspace bt709 \  
-max_muxing_queue_size 9999 \  
-f dash \  
out.mpd
```

In order to play out the produced content using the developed player (Task 3.4, LL3.4), the player resources need to be moved to the `/var/www/html` directory of the web server, and the `mainContentURL` variable from its `./js/index.js` file needs to be updated to link to the produced manifest file (`out.mpd` in the previous script).

5.8.4. Access to the Online Version of the Tool

Not applicable. However, the next online ViVIM demos make use of the low-latency DASH / HAS pipeline:

<https://media.i2cat.net/playertestv3/>
<https://media.i2cat.net/Respond-A/v2/#0>
<https://socialvr.i2cat.net/>

6. Depth-based 3D Video Pipeline

6.1. Brief Introduction to the Component / Tool

RGB-D (RGB and Depth) is an image-based format / technique mainly used to represent distance from the camera sensor, which can be adapted to produce / represent volumetric content, even in real-time. RGB-D sensors, like Intel RealSense or Azure Kinect, provide an easy-to-use depth estimation through time-of-flight technology, which can be later converted and visualized by rendering 3D point clouds. This representation format is quite efficient, with the resulting textures being fast to compute, with easily parallelizable algorithms, and being possible to use an accelerator such as the GPU to make most of the computations and offload a significant amount of work from the CPU. For instance, it is possible to compute data and modify them efficiently by assigning threads to calculate pixels, by using shaders, compute shaders or even CUDA.

Parallel programming, in particular for GPU computation, has a significant impact regarding real-time processing and visual quality, enabling for instance real-time processing of more than 300k points, which brings substantial benefits when compared to a pure real-time Point Cloud processing / encoding pipeline [19, 20], also adopted in ViViM, which struggles with point clouds of 80k points.

Figure 19 shows an example of how the RGB and Depth maps can be combined to create volumetric content.

Figure 19: Combination of RGB and Depth Maps to simulate different camera angles

However, this method also has some limitations. For instance, we are only displaying points that exist in an arbitrary space. In other words, these points do not have geometric positions (x y z), but they are displayed as a grid and the colors and positions are set to match the contents of both textures. For that reason, the camera properties are used to get an adequate calibration. We transform the depth map into a position map, which now has geometric information of the position of the elements in the environment. The following figure shows a visual representation of the position map.

Figure 20: Example of Position Map (containing X, Y, Z data)

By combining both textures it is possible to create volumetric scenes with thousands of points, which can be efficiently encoded/decoded and rendered. Figure 21 shows an example of the combination of these two textures.

Figure 21: Real time rendering of position + color maps

When applied to the real-time holo-portation scenarios envisioned in ViVIM, key additional challenges need to be addressed. For instance, it becomes essential to accurately remove the background scenes to achieve better human's reconstructions. To do so, a depth threshold can be set so that all values above the threshold are discarded, as they are outside the regions of interest. In addition, it is necessary to augment the capture and reconstruction processes with appropriate encoding, delivery, decoding and rendering processes to provide real-time audiovisual interactions based on RGB-D users' representations.

This section provides details on how the end-to-end RGB-D video pipeline has been developed and integrated within the ViVIM platform to provide support for multi-party holo-portation scenarios using a more lightweight (and potentially higher quality) representation format than when using the available Point Cloud pipeline inherited / adopted from the VR-Together project [19, 20].

Figure 22 shows the results of combining all the techniques previously discussed in a single-user holo-portation scenario. The top figure illustrates the grabbed image (at the origin client)

side on the left and the rendered image (at the target client) on the right, while the bottom figure shows an example of a user holo-ported in a VR scenario.

Figure 22: Examples of an RGB-D Representations in holo-ported scenarios

6.2. State-of-the-art and Provided Innovations / Benefits

The work in [21] provided initial empirical evidence that the use of real-time and realistic 3D human representations in VR environments results in an increased feeling of presence, as well as physical, emotional and user state recognition, compared to the use of animated synthetic avatars. The work in [22] also envisioned that the adoption of HMDs in conjunction with the use of single RGB-D cameras (e.g., Kinect) for the end-users' capture and representation can increase the engagement, feeling of immersion and enjoyable embodied telepresence compared to the use of traditional 2D social co-viewing tools. The work in [23] presented a video-based Social VR platform mainly focused on shared media consumption of stored content. In that platform, users are captured by a single RGB-D camera (Kinect), and the shared VR scenario is represented as a 360° static image. Then, the work in [24] proposed an experimental protocol and a questionnaire for evaluating Social VR experiences. By adopting a photo sharing use case, the experiment consisted of comparing the quality of interaction, social meaning and presence levels in three scenarios: (1) face-to-face; (2) Skype; and (3)

video-based Social VR (using the platform from [30]). The results of the experiment not only proved that the proposed evaluation methodology was appropriate (i.e. the designed VR questionnaire was highly reliable), but also that video-based (i.e. RGB-D based) Social VR provides an enhanced user experience compared to traditional video-conferencing tools, like Skype.

Based on the promising insights from [24], the work in [25] conducted two additional experiments to assess the benefits of realistic users' representations in Social VR scenarios. The first experiment consisted of recreating a shared video watching scenario in groups of two users, using the same three conditions as in [24]. The obtained results not only reinforced the appropriateness of the evaluation methodology proposed in [24], but also corroborated that the benefits of using realistic video-based representations over avatars also apply to this video co-watching use case, even finding out that the user experience and behaviours when using the video-based Social VR platform were comparable to those in face-to-face scenarios. These results, in turn, encouraged the development of a lightweight and low-cost Social VR platform, providing support for shared 3D environments and real-time captured volumetric representations of users by using Time Varying Meshes (TVM) as the representation format. Accordingly, the second experiment in [25] consisted of adopting the developed platform for evaluating a shared co-viewing experience by using a professionally created 3D VR episode as the shared content and not just 2D videos presented on a traditional screen, as in the first experiment. Although different technologies and content stimuli were used in the two experiments, similar results in terms of presence, togetherness and quality of interaction were obtained in both, which is an additional proof of evidence of the potential of using realistic volumetric representations in Social VR, despite the improvement margins of the used interactive volumetric media technology.

In [11], the Social VR platform from [23] is evolved in terms of its deployment in distributed scenarios, scalability (by integrating a Multipoint Control Unit (MCU)), and interactivity features.

The RGB-D video pipeline from ViVIM shares common features with the one from [11], but brings the advantage of not being limited to a web-based deployment, but instead it can leverage the potential of native applications in terms of interactivity, high-quality rendering and scalability features. In addition, the availability of a fully controllable end-to-end RGB-D pipeline opens up many research opportunities, not only regarding its appropriate fine tuning and optimization, but also regarding its comparison with other alternative representation formats (e.g., Point Clouds, 2D webcam users, avatars, etc.).

As discussed, realistic representations provide undoubtful benefits when compared to traditional 2D and avatar-based representations and provide many benefits in terms of real-time processing and visual perception when compared to 3D Point Cloud representations, but it needs to be validated via objective and subjective testing in the project.

The processing of RGB-D video along the pipelines provides many advantages, taking advantage of GPU-base processing. That way, it is possible to display higher quality representations using more points. In other words, we can render more than 300k points for a single representation using only a couple of textures, saving memory, bandwidth and encoding time. However, there are some limitations to this method, for instance: points, positions and projections are calculated in parallel which makes these computations GPU intensive and appropriate hardware is needed. Another important limitation is calibrating several cameras to achieve a full-body reconstruction. It is important to take into consideration intrinsic calibration of each camera to build accurate textures in 3D spaces.

6.3. Architecture

The software adopts a classical server-client architecture, as for typical state-of-the-art delivery pipelines. Its integration within the end-to-end ViVIM architecture is shown in Figure 1. In particular, the pipeline connects RGB-D capturing sensors with the origin native client where the RGB-D reconstruction and encoding processes are performed. State-of-the-art 2D video codecs (e.g., H264) can be used in the involved encoding / decoding processes. The encoded media streams are delivered via the Orchestrator (or the MCU in evolved versions of this pipeline, to be reported in future versions of this deliverable) to the target clients, where the decoding and rendering processes are performed.

6.4. Components and APIs

1. RGB-D capture: K4A (Azure Kinect) devices provide two different inputs to our system, a color video stream, and a depth video stream, each one of those streams is read using its own device thread. We extract that information and store the frames in different textures, as shown in the following snippet:

```

_colorMap = new RenderTexture
    (width, height, 0, RenderTextureFormat.Default);
_colorMap.enableRandomWrite = true;
_colorMap.Create();

_positionMap = new RenderTexture
    (width, height, 0, RenderTextureFormat.ARGBFloat);
_positionMap.enableRandomWrite = true;

```

2. RGB-D transformations: Once we have stored each frame in both textures, we use the camera properties to calculate the geometric position of each of the points in the particle system. We use those properties to determine how to unproject the texture from 2D space to 3D space. The following snippet illustrates this process:

```

Parallel.For(0, height, y => {
    Float2 v2; // 2D Space
    Float3 v3; // Resultant unprojected 3D space
    bool isValid;

    v2.y = y;
    var offs = width * 2 * y;

    for (var x = 0; x < width; x++)
    {
        v2.x = x;

        k4a_calibration_2d_to_3d
            (ref calibration,
             ref v2, 1,
             CalibrationDeviceType.Depth,
             CalibrationDeviceType.Depth,
             out v3,
             out isValid);

        table[offs++] = v3.x; //stores the x position of the particle
        table[offs++] = v3.y; //stores the y position of the particle
    }
});

```

We store the projection data in a list and afterwards we combine it with the depth texture. Each point checks its depth value, if it's bigger than a given threshold, we assign its alpha value to 1 to make it transparent and be discarded when rendering.

```
float mask = depth > 0 && depth < MaxDepth;
float z = lerp(0, depth, mask);
// Map
ColorMap[id] = float4(color, mask);
PositionMap[id] = float4(xy, z, mask);
DepthMap[id] = float4(z, z, z, mask);
```

These calculations are performed in parallel, using one thread per pixel, and we write the result in different buffers that are used for rendering.

3. RGB-D encoding: Once all the buffers have been computed, we fuse the depth and the color textures into a single texture. That way, all the information is stored together and the transmission is done through a single stream.

```
if (!isFrameReady && timeToFrame < Time.realtimeSinceStartup) {
    positionMap = transformedPosition.GetPixels32();
    colorMap = transformedColor.GetPixels32();

    positionMap.CopyTo(RGBD, 0);
    colorMap.CopyTo(RGBD, positionMap.Length);

    isFrameReady = true;
}
```

After both textures are combined, we store the frame data in a thread safe queue and we encode it using ffmpeg, with H.264 codec, to transmit the data over the network.

```
reader = new RGBDReader(width, height, fps, vfx, this, encoderQueue);
encoder = new VideoEncoder(new VideoEncoder.Setup() { codec = codec, width = width,
height = height, fps = fps, bitrate = bitrate }, encoderQueue, null, decoderQueue,
null);
decoder = new VideoDecoder(codec, decoderQueue, null, preparerQueue, null);
preparer = new VideoPreparer(preparerQueue, null);
```

4. RGB-D delivery: We write the data from the RGBD buffer to the out queue using the previous configuration:

```
if (outQueue.IsClosed())
    return;
try {
    lock (this) {
        if (isFrameReady) {
            Color32ArrayToByteArray(RGBD, outQueue);
        }
    }
} catch (OperationCanceledException) {
}
```

5. RGB-D decoding: Once the data are received, the information is split into the original textures and they are sent to the rendering process.

```
if (texture == null) {
```

```

        texture = new Texture2D(decoder != null ? decoder.Width :
width, decoder != null ? decoder.Height : height, TextureFormat.RGB24, false, false);
    }
try {

    texture.LoadRawTextureData(preparer.GetVideoPointer(preparer.videFrameSize),
preparer.videFrameSize);
    texture.Apply();

    receivedTexture = texture.GetPixels32();
    System.Array.Copy(receivedTexture, 0, splitColor, 0, receivedTexture.Length /
2);
    System.Array.Copy(receivedTexture, receivedTexture.Length / 2, splitPosition,
0, splitPosition.Length);

    controller.SetBuffers(splitPosition, splitColor);

    destinationColor.material.mainTexture = controller.ColorMap;
    destinationColor.transform.localScale = new Vector3(1, 1,
controller.ColorMap.height / (float)controller.ColorMap.width);
    destinationPosition.material.mainTexture = controller.PositionMap;
    destinationPosition.transform.localScale = new Vector3(1, 1,
controller.PositionMap.height / (float)controller.PositionMap.width);

```

6. RGB-D rendering: To render the user representation we use Unity VFX Graph to create a particle system, which assigns each particle a position in space combined with the color texture that is read from the device. This is performed using the GPU to both fetch and display data.

6.5. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

6.5.1. System / Processing Requirements

The RGB-D video pipeline does not bring stringent system / processing requirements, beyond the ability to grab the data from an RGB-D sensor in real-time (e.g. at 30 fps using Azure Kinect), run a Unity build involving 3D virtual environments and multi-party audiovisual communications, and ideally being able to use the GPU for a more efficient and powerful processing of all RGB-D and associated immersive content elements.

It has been tested satisfactorily by using different VR ready laptops, although further functionality and performance tests will be conducted and reported in future versions of this deliverable.

6.5.2. Performance / Scalability KPIs

The Depth-based video pipeline has been shown to be able to process up to 300K points in real-time when using a VR ready laptop, which is a significantly larger number of points that when using state-of-the-art Point Cloud codecs.

However, further functionality and performance tests will be conducted to determine performance and scalability KPIs, and will be reported in future versions of this deliverable.

6.6. Integration Status

The Depth-based video pipeline has been successfully installed and run on different Windows VR ready desktops and laptops, when using inputs from Azure Kinect sensors. In addition, it

has been tested that the produced and processed content has been correctly interpreted and presented on the native Unity-based player (Task 3.4) when exchanged via the Orchestrator. Although future efforts will be devoted to integrating this pipeline with the cloud-based MCU, it can be considered that its integration with the ViVIM platform has already been successful. Its relationship with other components, blocks and modules from the ViVIM platform architecture is represented in Figure 1. In particular, it can be seen that this pipeline connects the capture sub-systems (RGB-D sensors) connected to the origin player to the target client player(s) via the Orchestrator or MCU, carrying out the media stream with the realistic representation of the users captured in real-time.

The pilot actions to be conducted to test this tool will shed more light on its adequate performance, behaviour and perceived quality when using different types of devices, over different scenarios, and when compared to other representation formats / pipelines.

6.7. Distribution Model

The exact distribution model for the updated version of this tool still needs to be assessed, and will be indicated in a future version of this deliverable.

6.8. Installation, Setup and Usage Guides

6.8.1. Access to the Code

The code of this pipeline is available at the Bitbucket repository of i2CAT:

<https://bitbucket.i2cat.net/projects/VIVIM/repos/rgbd-player/browse>

Credentials to access and download it can be given, if requested, to mia.support@i2cat.net or to the project's coordinator sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

6.8.2. Installation and Setup

This pipeline is integrated with the whole ViVIM platform for holo-portation, no additional packages or downloads are required. This package includes the following dependencies: VRTCore (core libraries for the holo-portation platform), Socket.IO, FFmpeg, and K4A libraries and DLLs.

6.8.3. Tool Usage

Key Steps were described in section 6.4

6.8.4. Access to the Online Version of the Tool

Not applicable. This tool is not provided as a self-contained tool per se, but can be activated / selected when using the native version of the ViVIM holo-portation platform.

7. WebRTC Remote Rendering Plugin

7.1. Brief Introduction to the Component / Tool

High-quality VR and holo-portation services require high bandwidth and processing requirements at the client side, which are not always available. To overcome these challenges and limitations, Remote Rendering components have been devised in the last years, which the goal of providing rendered 2D streams (and thus requiring lower processing and bandwidth requirements) to lightweight clients or to clients connected to low capacity networks.

In this context, a new WebRTC Remote Rendering plugin has been developed to be able to provide an output 2D stream from a Unity player, regardless of the content modalities being played out. It is based on the adoption and configuration of an existing WebRTC plugin for Unity and of a Traversal Using Relays around NAT (TURN) server to allow for WebRTC based communications with remote web players. That way, the hardware requirements to be able to participate in multi-party holo-portation services, although as a passive spectator without visual representation, are significantly reduced, also enabling scalable scenarios.

7.2. State-of-the-art and Provided Innovations / Benefits

Remote Rendering solutions and strategies have become popular for a variety of VR services (e.g. [26, 27]) to provide support to lightweight and untethered VR clients, or to clients connected to low capacity networks. In addition, the potential of WebRTC for web-based remote rendering of computer games has been recently explored (e.g. [28]). However, as far as authors know, no other standard-compliant web-based Remote Rendering features for 3D volumetric holo-portation services have been proposed so far by the scientific community, thus being an innovative and pioneering contribution of ViVIM.

7.3. Architecture

When running multi-party holo-portation services in ViVIM, an Orchestrator is used to manage users, scenes and sessions. Such session management services have been augmented with another decoupled server service that allows the participation of extra users via WebRTC, receiving a 2D rendered stream from a reference Unity player from the chosen session. These new participants / spectators are connected via a web client.

Figure 23 provides a high-level overview of how this tool / plugin is integrated in the end-to-end ViVIM platform, with the involved components represented in green color.

This plugin will be evolved in future releases to incorporate different features, including potentially: (i) bidirectional audio communications between the web clients and other native VR clients; (ii) allow a remote interaction of the virtual camera (in terms of viewpoint and direction); (iii) support for 360° scene capturing; (iv) support for multiple virtual cameras, and thus interactive web clients, from each VR native client; (v) include a more advanced communication with the Orchestrator to provide scalability and awareness of the connected web clients in shared sessions.

Figure 23: High-level architecture of the WebRTC plugin for Remote Rendering (involved components represented in green color)

7.4. Components and APIs

The main components of the WebRTC Remote Rendering tool are:

- A WebRTC Unity plugin¹² installed as part of the Unity player for the holo-portation services (Task 3.4)
- A WebRTC server (implemented in Python) to negotiate ICE candidates.
- A STUN/TURN server to allow negotiations behind NAT scenarios.
- A web client to connect to the rendered WebRTC from the Unity player.

All these components have been configured and modified to provide the targeted remote rendering features in the ViVIM holo-portation services.

Future releases of this software component will result in evolved versions of such components and the incorporation of new ones, to be reported in future versions of this deliverable.

7.5. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

7.5.1. System / Processing Requirements

On the one hand, a thin PC / laptop without a particular graphic card, or even a mobile device, would be enough to get connected and remote rendered from a multi-party holo-portation, or in general VR, session by using this tool. This is the key strength of this tool.

¹² <https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/com.unity.webrtc> Last Access in December 2021

On the other hand, the same machine used for the Orchestrator could be shared for the installation and deployment of the WebRTC servers and of the web client part (e.g. configured through nginx). The most important requirement is to open the appropriate ports in the firewall to enable the WebRTC communications.

7.5.2. Performance / Scalability KPIs

Resources usage, performance and scalability tests will be conducted in the upcoming months, and reported in future versions of this deliverable.

7.6. Integration Status

The tool has been already integrated within the ViVIM platform, and some preliminary demos have been conducted. However, it is still necessary to optimize and extend its implementation to provide support for bi-directional audio communications, some interaction features (e.g. remote control of the virtual camera), and extend its scalability features.

7.7. Distribution Model

The WebRTC plugin for Unity being adopted to develop this tool is available under an Apache 2.0 License: <https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/com.unity.webrtc> An open-source web server to host the web clients can be adopted (e.g. nginx, Apache). Finally, different versions for the WebRTC-related servers can be explored.

The exact distribution model for the updated version of this tool still needs to be assessed, and will be indicated in a future version of this deliverable.

7.8. Installation, Setup and Usage Guides

7.8.1. Access to the Code

The WebRTC plugin for Unity can be downloaded from: <https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/com.unity.webrtc>

The complete code for this tool will be shared and documented in future versions of this deliverable, once being more thoroughly tested and other relevant features are added. Meanwhile, the current code can be shared if requested to mia.support@i2cat.net or to the project's coordinator sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

7.8.2. Installation and Setup

This documentation will be provided in a future version of the deliverable.

7.8.3. Tool Usage

This documentation will be provided in a future version of the deliverable.

7.8.4. Access to the Online Version of the Tool

The current version of the Remote Rendering tool is available online at: <https://media.i2cat.net/holomitWeb/>

However, a VR or holo-portation session needs to be activated, and with one of the Unity players with the WebRTC feature activate, in order to join that session via the web client (webinar-like in the current version).

8. Conclusions

Multi-platform delivery (processing, transmission and reception) become fundamental steps of every end-to-end multimedia service. This deliverable has reported on the different software tools developed within the umbrella of the ViVIM project to deal with various aspects of multi-platform delivery for the envisioned use cases and media formats, including 2D video, 360° video, RGB-D streams carrying out human's representations, and even rendered 2D streams from 3D VR environments integrating heterogeneous content modalities. While many of the software tools and/or their sub-components are adopted state-of-the-art pieces, many others become innovative and reference implementations, becoming key parts of the diverse novel scenarios and use cases enabled by the ViVIM technological contributions.

While functional and tested versions of all software tools are available at the time of writing, and have been reported in this deliverable, their design, development and evaluation will continue in the coming months. Likewise, their associated improvement and novelties, as well as extra details, will be provided in future versions of the deliverable.

Finally, the contributions from this deliverable will be more clearly understood once reading the closely related LL3.4 from Task 3.4, which reports on the associate interaction and display software tools that become the final points of the reported delivery and session management tools / components.

9. Referències

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10. ANNEX: Usage Guide of the Adobe Premiere Pro Plugin for editing multi-format and multi-screen experiences (i360Editor)

10.1. Introduction

This Annex provides a tutorial of the features provided by the Adobe Premiere Pro Plugin for editing multi-format and multi-screen experiences (i360Editor), alongside some illustrative exercises with the required media resources to complete them.

10.1.1. Resources download

The software and all the necessary content resources to carry out this tutorial can be downloaded at:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1YCUJGILVujCjMhJCuahepy7aqZ69rhdu?usp=sharing>

10.2. Resources download

To install the plugin, it will be necessary to have the latest version of Premiere Pro and then run the *360Editor_PPRO_extension_installer_v0.22.1c.exe* executable located in the above link.

10.2. Plugin Overview

This Annex provides a tutorial of the features provided by the Adobe Premiere Pro Plugin for editing multi-format and multi-screen experiences (i360Editor), alongside some illustrative exercises with the required media resources to complete them.

This tool is an Adobe Premiere Pro extension that provides three new add-ons for enabling the editing of interactive experiences, combining multi-format 2D and 360° video assets, to be played out in single- and multi-screen scenarios, by using both traditional and Virtual Reality (VR) displays. The new add-ons include: (i) two video effects; (10) one pack of transitions for immersive content elements; and (10i) one extension panel that allows to configure a set of parameters, add interactive elements, and finally export the edited project using standard-compliant metadata to be processed by an associated 360° media player.

Each of these features are introduced next.

10.2.1. Video Effects

This extension adds an extra package with two video effects into the *Effects panel*, under the *i360Editor* plugin folder. The usage of both effects is exactly the same as that when using other effects from Adobe Premiere Pro: the user only needs to drag and drop the effect over the desired clip and control its parameters through the *Effect controls* panel.

Let's see these effects in detail.

10.2.1.1. 360 projection mapping

The base of an immersive omnidirectional scene is a 360° video, but there are different options to represent that content modality in a 2D space. The most common format is the equirectangular projection (Figure 10.1), as it is very intuitive. However, it is not the optimal representation format in terms of encoding / processing, because distortion is added on the poles in the transformation from a sphere to a plain, adding also pixel redundancy. Other representation formats, like cubic (Figure 10.2) or pyramidal, become more efficient in terms of processing, but more difficult to visually interpret while editing.

Adobe Premiere Pro only natively supports the equirectangular projection. However, a new plugin effect *360 Projection Mapping* has been developed to provide support for cubic projection. This new effect additionally performs a real time transformation from cubic to equirectangular projection to preview the video in Adobe Premiere Pro in a more understandable / intuitive way.

The plugin also allows to change the horizontal and vertical offset to correct directions in the 3D space. By playing with these parameters, the producer can change the point of interest (Figure 10.2), and also modify or correct the calibration of the cameras due to a bad positioning on the capture process.

Figure 10.1: Equirectangular projection (applying 360 projection Mapping to a cubic input)

Figure 10.2: Cubemap projection input with 360 projection Mapping deactivated

Figure 10.3: Equirectangular projection after applying horizontal offset to change the point of interest

10.2.1.2. Portals

This is a new effect that allows the content creator to introduce elements of interactivity. In particular, the effect allows adding a dynamic video insert, allowing viewers to influence the displayed content (e.g., show/hide elements, switch between views). It can be a rectangular insert from a directional camera or a static graphic (Figure 10.4).

Figure 10.4: Directive graphic with Portal effect deactivated

Portals can be inserts on the 3D world (*World reference*), meaning they stay always in the same 3D (x,y,z) coordinates, or they can be overlaid on the screen (*User reference*).

A world reference portal (Figure 10.5) can be positioned everywhere on the 3D scene, always looking at the camera. Its position is based on XYZ polar coordinates mapped on a 2D preview, being (0,0) the center of the 2D composition. These last values are based on degrees. *Vertical position* allows values on the range (-90,90), while *Horizontal position* on the range (-180,180) to cover all the range of the sphere. The distance position (Z) is computed depending on the track position on the sequence, as explained next.

Figure 10.5: Directive graphic with Portal effect activated and set as World reference

User reference portals (Figure 10.6) are positioned in a 2D space because they are overlaid on the screen. As screen sizes can be different on each device, relative values for their position on the screen are used. These values are percentages, being (0,0) the upper-left corner and (100,100) the lower-right corner.

Figure 10.6: Directive graphic with Portal effect activated and set as User reference

The editor can define its size, position and visibility using the *Effect Controls* panel, and it can also define some interactions between elements, using the *onActionStart* field and selecting the target element. That way, when clicking on this portal, i.e., pressing it on a tablet or staring at it on a Head Mounted Display (HMD), the player can e.g. show or hide another element on the scene.

Typically, Adobe Premier Pro tracks act like layers in the composition and a top layer covers the ones at its back. That means the tracks on the bottom must be the omnidirectional videos, then the world reference portals must be added, and finally the user reference ones. We use this layer-based concept to generate the export metadata, using the tracks position and type to compute distances, to avoid collisions between elements. With this purpose, three distance zones have been defined: (i) User reference portals are located at distance 0.3 from the camera and always follow its position; (10) World reference portals are located between 0.31 and 0.8 and are static in the 3D world; and (10i) 360 videos from 0.81 to 1.

This effect is integrated with Adobe Premiere Pro built-in preview, which facilitates a fine-tuning of the multi-device experience. Premiere Pro also includes an internal VR preview where you can navigate across the 360 scene. The problem we found with it is that the VR preview is a 2D projection of the scene, so it is suitable for *World reference* portals because, but *User reference* portals are treated as a world reference ones and do not follow the camera (Figure 10.7). Also, as there was no way to test interactivity options, we added our own custom preview explained in Section 2.3.1 of this document.

Figure 10.7: Differences with User portal on native Pro VR preview (left) and on the developed custom preview (right)

10.2.2. Transitions

For smooth opening and closing of *Portals* and switching between omnidirectional videos, a set of basic transitions compatible with the associated 360° player (Task 3.4) was implemented.

These transitions are Dissolve, Iris Open/Close, Wipe Open/Close and Wipe Left/Right:

- Dissolve: The dissolve transition is when one scene gradually mixes into another. Figure 10.8 shows an example of this transition applied between two clips.

Figure 10.8: Dissolve transition

- Iris Open/Close: The iris transition reproduces the effect of opening (Iris Open) or closing (Iris Close) the iris of a camera lens.

Figure 10.9: Iris Open transition

- Wipe Open/Close: The wipe effect replaces one scene to another moving the preceding scene out of the way. In wipe open, that effect starts in the centre of screen (Figure 9), and in wipe close this effect starts on the two extremes of screen.

Figure 10.10: Wipe Open transition

- Wipe Left/Right: In a wipe left, the effect starts on the left side of screen, as shown in Figure 10, and in a wipe right the transition effect starts on the other side of screen.

Figure 10.11: Wipe Left transition

10.2.3. Export Panel

This panel (Figure 10.12) is the most important piece of the extension, because it generates the data that allows the understanding between the production and delivery modules.

Figure 10.12: Export Panel

To open the 360Editor Export Panel, go to Window > Extensions > 360Editor (see Figure 10.13)

Figure 10.13: How to Open the Export Panel

The panel lists all the video tracks on the active sequence and allows users to select their type (directive/spherical) and target devices (HMD/Tablet/TV). It extends the standard Adobe Premiere Pro editing process, in which video tracks are generally mixed together in a sequence, to edit videos in a common sequence but targeting different devices for media presentation.

With this approach it is possible to assign a single track to be rendered on different devices, but to keep a common timeline for all of them, thus without the need for creating a sequence for each device, making it easier and keep an in-sync presentation of all associated media elements. The aim is to mix omnidirectional, traditional video footage and images into an appealing multi-device end user experience.

This Export panel also allows easy export of the final project to the suitable format (media files and metadata) that represents the multi-device content. This format is used for delivery and multi-device audience consumption. It is possible to define the output quality (resolution and bitrate) for spherical and directive (TV) videos, while a fixed low resolution (426x240) is typically used for the portals given their reduced size on the scene. After defining these parameters, all the tracks are rendered with a single click on the *Export* button, which also includes the generation of the associated metadata.

10.2.3.1. Custom preview

The panel also includes a custom external preview, for a static check of the composition status in the associated 360° player. In its preview, the user reference portals are attached to the screen instead of fixed in the 3D world, as it happens in the Adobe Premiere Pro VR preview (Figure 10.14), and it is also possible to test a little bit the interactivity between elements on the same sequence. This preview is generated each time the user clicks the *Preview* button, being a static preview. By clicking the *Preview* button, a QR code (Figure 12) is generated and displayed in the *Export* panel. That QR code allows to preview the composition directly on mobile devices, by scanning it.

Figure 10.14: QR code generated for external preview

10.3. How to Use the Tool

10.3.1. Introduction

If you are a Premiere Pro experienced user it will probably be very intuitive to use these tools, but the Export panel can be something quite new and confusing. To teach the basic functionalities of our extension, we have designed a series of exercises.

10.3.2. Exercise 1. A simple scene with 360 and portals

In this exercise you will create one omnidirectional scene based in a 360 panorama and you will learn how to insert directive media as portals. More specifically, you will:

- Learn how to use the 360 projection Mapping and Portal effects.
- Insert 2 directive inserts in an omnidirectional scene (one user referenced, one world referenced).
- Learn how to use the custom preview. Try both tablet and HMD.
- Learn how to export content using the Export Panel, and include differences in export for tablet, HMD and TV.

Steps:

1. Create a new project and import the media from the folder *Practice1* into a bin called *Practice1*.
2. Drag and drop the omnidirectional clip (*360_livingroom.mp4*) in the empty timeline to create a new sequence matching the parameters of the current video. Check the resolution is set to equirectangular resolution (aspect ratio 4096x2048) and rename the sequence *Practice1*.

3. Watch the video and insert a marker on the exact frame where the kid and the father's hands make contact, that will help you to sync different tracks. You can use the VR preview to have a closer view.
4. Now Drag and drop the directive video (*directive_livingroom.mov*) on the track right above the 360 one (V2). Right click on the video on the clip recently inserted on the timeline and select Scale to frame size option. You will notice the video now fits on the preview monitor.
5. Do the same process as step 4 of inserting a marker, but now for the 2D track. At this point the screen should be similar to Figure 10.15.
6. Now use the previous markers to put the two tracks in sync and cut the videos in a way that they start and end at the same time, as shown in Figure 10.16.

Figure 10.15: Screenshot of practice1 after inserting the markers to the clips

Figure 10.16: On top the markers aligned. On bottom both tracks with same duration

7. Drag and drop the *immersiaTV_logo.png* to the video track V3. Right click on the clip to select Scale as frame size. Now set a similar duration to the other video tracks.
8. Copy the directive clip from V2 and paste it to V4.
9. Go to the Effects panel and find the i360Editor video effects. Drag and drop the 360 Projection mapping over the 360 clip on V1. Hide the other tracks in order to view only the 360 track.
10. Select the 360 clip and go to the Effects control panel and check the 360 Projection Mapping effect appears on the list. This 360 clip has an equirectangular projection. Check that the field Input projection is set to Equirectangular. Change the horizontal offset value to 43.00 in order to have the kid in the center of the Program monitor (Note that the values of offset are degrees and the center of the original video is the coordinate [0,0]). That will be the initial view when playing the content. You can activate the grid view by clicking above the title of the effect on the Effect Controls panel and you will have something similar to Figure 10.17.

Figure 10.17: Using 360 Projection mapping effect with the grid

11. Unhide the track V2. Drag and drop the Portal effect from the Effects panel over the clip in V2. Have you noticed anything? This is a Portal. Now you can configure its parameters on the Effect controls panel. Set the portal as World Reference, Horizontal position to -35 and Size to 15%.
12. Now unhide V3 and apply a Portal effect over the clip on V3. Click on the effect title to display the grid and set the parameters to be a User Reference, with Y position to 5%, X position to 95% and Size to 15%. Note that the User reference portals coordinates are different and use percentage values for a better adaptation to all kinds of screens.
13. Change the view on the Program monitor to VR video display. Note that the User reference portal behavior is the same as the World Reference one. That's why we have our own static preview. But before running it let's rename the video tracks for and easier usage. From V1 to V4 rename the tracks as *360_livingroom*, *tv_portal*, *logo_portal* and *tv_track*.
14. Now let's do the magic. Go to *Window>Extensions* and select 360Editor. This is our 360Editor Export Panel. What you see now is the current sequence you are working on, listing all of its tracks.
15. First of all set the view of the *360_livingroom* track to 360. You see, the name helps you! The devices columns you see on the right allow you to select which track has to be exported for Head-mounted displays, tablets/smartphones or TVs, so you don't need to create a sequence for each device and it also helps you to sync all the tracks. Select HMD device for tracks *360_livingroom* and *tv_portal*. Select Tablet device for *360_livingroom*, *tv_portal* and *logo_portal*. Select TV for the *tv_track*. It should look like Figure 10.18.

Figure 10.18: Export panel after configuring the view and devices

16. Now that everything is configured you can press the Preview button. It will generate a preview of the current instant on the timeline where your time bar is. So move the time bar first to the desired point! Now you can visualize the Tablet view by scanning the QR code with your phone or tablet. Be sure that you are connected to the same network in the computer and in your device, or it will not work.

17. Are you happy with the results? Then last thing to do is to export the content in a suitable format for the 360 Web player. To do so, you just need to set the Export resolution for Spherical and Directive media, and the bitrate. Next thing to do is to activate the toggle buttons for Media and Metadata, and press the Export button. Select the folder where you want to export the content and just wait for the export to end its process. Your content is ready!

10.3.3. Exercise 2. Multi-Camera Experience

In this exercise you will learn how to:

- Create a scene with a TV track and multiple 360 videos synchronized in time
- Use portals to switch between different omnidirectional videos
- Introduce a TV portal

Steps:

In the same project, import the media from the folder *Practice2* into a bin called *Practice2*.

1. Drag and drop the omnidirectional clip (*base_360.mp4*) in the empty timeline to create a new sequence matching the parameters of the current video. Check the resolution is set to equirectangular resolution (aspect ratio 4096x2048) and rename the sequence *Practice2*.
2. Add two more 360 clips *cam1_360.mp4* and *cam2_360.mp4* to the tracks V2 and V3, respectively.
3. Drag and drop the 360 Projection Mapping effect from the Effects panel to each of the 360 clips. You can check in the Effect controls that it is already set as equirectangular projection. These videos are synchronized in time, it means less work to do.
4. Let's add the portals to control the multi-camera experience. Add the next .png files in order and each one in a new track:
 - 360_base_tablet.png
 - 360_cam1_tablet.png
 - 360_cam2_tablet.png
 - campo_tablet.png
 - tv_portal_tablet.png
 - 360_base_hmd.png
 - 360_cam1_hmd.png
 - 360_cam2_hmd.png

Set them to start around second 5 of the timeline and to end 5 seconds before the 360 video clips ends, and remember to right click on them and set Scale to frame size option.

5. Before setting the portals parameters let's add also the tv track, that way we are done inserting the media. Drag and drop the *tv_maintrack.mp4* in a new track on top (you will need to hide it to see the contents below).
6. Drag and drop the Portal effect over each of the .png clips (not over the TV track). At this point the timeline should look similar to Figure 10.19.

Figure 10.19: View of the timeline after inserting all the media

7. Rename all the video tracks using the same name as the clips. That will help to compose the scene.
8. Now we are going to set the parameters of the portals to have a nice composition. In this step we also are going to set the interactivity that will allow the user to switch between the 360 cameras. Set the parameters to all the portals following the Table 1. Note that for the tablet we are using User reference portals but for the HMD we use World reference ones. That's why in the HMD you need to point the portals to do the click, and if these portals are following you there is no way to do it.

Track	Reference	Vertical position	Horizontal Position	Size	onActionStart
<i>360_base_tablet</i>	User	85%	0%	20%	base_360
<i>360_cam1_tablet</i>	User	85%	0%	20%	cam1_360
<i>360_cam2_tablet</i>	User	85%	0%	20%	cam2_360
<i>campo_tablet</i>	User	100%	0%	20%	None
<i>tv_portal_tablet</i>	User	0%	100%	20%	tv_maintrack
<i>360_base_hmd</i>	World	-30	0	20%	base_360
<i>360_cam1_hmd</i>	World	-30	-15	20%	cam1_360
<i>360_cam2_hmd</i>	World	-30	15	20%	cam2_360

Table 10.1: Settings of the portals for a multi-camera experience

9. Let's explain the composition a little bit. With these settings when a click is performed over one of the elements that start with '360_', the 360 background video will switch to its corresponding camera. *Campo_tablet* is just for helping to understand camera position, so it is not interactive. *Tv_portal_tablet* is pointing to the tv_maintrack, so instead of switching the 360 video, it will activate the same view as the main TV, that can be interesting for repeating views of the highlighted actions on the match.
10. Why don't we add some transitions to make the elements appear in a smooth way? Go to the Effects panel and look for the i360Editor folder inside the Video Transitions. You can use IrisOpen and IrisClose for the beginning and end of the 360 clips. WipeOpen

and Dissolve for the beginning end of the tv track, and Dissolve for the beginning end of the portals, for example.

11. Now open the 360Editor export panel. We are going to set the parameters for previewing and exporting the composition. Set the parameters as shown in Figure 10.20.
12. Now you can preview the results by clicking the preview button and scanning the QR code with your smartphone. Remember to be connected to the same network as the computer or it will not work. It should look something similar to Figure 10.21.
13. Last step, export the content. Set the Export resolution for Spherical and Directive media, and the bitrate. Activate the toggle buttons for Media and Metadata, and press the Export button. Select the folder where you want to export the content and just wait for the export to end its process. Your content is ready!

Tracks	View			
tv_maintrack	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
360_cam2_hmd	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
360_cam1_hmd	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
360_base_hmd	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
tv_portal_tablet	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
campo_tablet	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
360_cam2_tablet	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
360_cam1_tablet	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
360_base_tablet	2D 360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
cam2_360	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
cam1_360	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
base_360	2D 360	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 10.20: Settings for previewing and exporting the multi-camera content

Figure 10.21: Preview of the result composition in tablet (top) and HMD (bottom)